

Research Data Management Guidelines for the DFG Priority Program SPP 2419 HyCAM

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1. Introduction

Research Data Management (RDM) is a fundamental principle in good scientific practice. It aims to ensure that research data are generated, handled, and preserved in a secure, sustainable, and reusable manner in accordance with the **FAIR** principles [1], thereby guaranteeing that data remain findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable over the long term.

National and international funding agencies, including the DFG and the European Union, increasingly require compliance with established RDM standards as a prerequisite for research funding. In line with RDM DFG guidelines [2], the coordination project of the DFG Priority Programme SPP 2419 *Hydrogen-based Fuel Combustion using Additive Manufacturing* (HyCAM) actively promotes and monitors the implementation of good RDM practices throughout the programme's duration. SPP 2419 HyCAM comprises ten research projects, each structured into three interconnected subprojects: experimental combustion, numerical combustion, and additive manufacturing. Given its highly interdisciplinary nature, the significant number of participating projects, and the strong synergies across research areas, the programme is expected to generate a substantial volume of diverse research data. Proper and coordinated data management is therefore essential to ensure high-quality, FAIR-compliant scientific outputs, to facilitate collaboration, and to achieve the programme's scientific objectives.

Effective RDM supports researchers in their work, enhances transparency and reproducibility, and accelerates knowledge discovery through responsible data publication. Centralized and structured data management, from planning to long-term archiving, ensures accessibility, usability, and the continuous evolution of best practices.

Building on the research data management strategy and policy implemented at the Institute for Combustion and Technology [3], the following guidelines outline the overall research data management approach adopted within the DFG Priority Programme SPP 2419 HyCAM. They further define the practices that researchers are encouraged to follow throughout the entire research data lifecycle (see Figure 1). RDM spans the full research process: it begins during the planning phase, continues through data generation, processing, and analysis, and extends beyond project completion through data preservation and publication, thereby enabling long-term reuse and the initiation of new research cycles. Decisions made at each stage influence subsequent phases.

Figure 1: Conceptual representation of the research data lifecycle, illustrating the successive stages of data planning, generation, processing, preservation, and reuse

Effective RDM includes defining data sources, documentation standards, and quality assurance procedures during planning. During data collection and analysis, datasets must be systematically documented, organized, validated, and securely stored. After project completion, relevant datasets should be preserved in sustainable formats and deposited in certified repositories with adequate metadata and licensing to ensure long-term accessibility and reuse.

Considering the data lifecycle is often the first step toward drafting a high-quality **Data Management Plan (DMP)**. A DMP is a living document that systematically outlines how research data are handled throughout a project. It provides a structured framework to plan, implement, and monitor data management measures. As projects increase in size and complexity, DMP management becomes more demanding and should therefore be integrated into the overall project management structure. To ensure efficient workflows and avoid duplication of effort, all project members have been encouraged to use a common tool for creating and maintaining DMPs. In particular, the **NFDI4Ing Research Data Management Organiser (RDMO)**, provided by NDFI.

For effective software management, code and other suitable text-based materials should be maintained in a Git repository. Git-based version control ensures transparent tracking of changes, structured collaboration, and long-term traceability. Repositories should be hosted on institutional platforms (e.g., RWTH GitLab) and managed in accordance with applicable licensing and confidentiality requirements. Ultimately, for the practical implementation of the data management strategy within SPP 2419 HyCAM, the use of **Coscine (Collaborative Scientific Integration Environment)** is recommended as the central platform for documenting, organizing, and storing research outputs. This includes journal publications, validation datasets, experimental measurement data, simulation inputs, and simulation results. Coscine provides a shared online environment that supports secure storage, collaborative access, and long-term archiving of research.

Figure 2 provides an overview of the RDM framework adopted in SPP 2419 HyCAM. It highlights three core components: (i) data management planning, (ii) software code management, and (iii) research data storage and documentation. The following sections describe the objectives and implementation of each component.

Figure 2: Research Data Management workflow for the DFG Priority Program SPP 2419 HyCAM

2. Data Management Planning

Data Management Plans (DMPs) are a central instrument for structuring research data management (RDM) in academic projects. The European Commission requires a DMP as part of project proposals and specifies that it should address all stages of the research data lifecycle. At the same time, it emphasizes that DMPs should be meaningfully integrated into project workflows in order to enhance their practical value and avoid being perceived merely as administrative obligations [4].

In Germany, the National Research Data Infrastructure ([NFDI](#)), comprising more than 270 institutional members, supports initiatives such as [DMP4NFDI](#) to standardize DMP content and provide the technical infrastructure necessary for their effective use. Despite these efforts, DMPs are often underestimated in practice, and their successful implementation typically requires dedicated coordination, usually by data managers or data stewards.

Within the DFG Priority Program SPP 2419 HyCAM, a centralized and structured approach to DMP management has therefore been adopted. All DMPs are created and maintained using the [NFDI4Ing RDMO](#) platform. [NFDI4Ing](#), the engineering sciences consortium within NFDI, provides standardized templates, interoperable infrastructures, and support services to promote FAIR and sustainable research data practices. In HyCAM, drafting a DMP via NFDI4Ing is a mandatory prerequisite and represents a foundational step toward transparent and harmonized data management across the entire Priority Program. To ensure consistency, a tailored SPP 2419 DMP template, developed in collaboration with the RWTH University Library, has been integrated into the NFDI4Ing RDMO platform. Structured as a questionnaire, this catalog provides standardized guidance for researchers and PIs, enabling efficient and coherent DMP preparation while reducing individual effort.

Building on this common framework, HyCAM applies a hierarchical project structure within RDMO, displayed by the schematic in Figure 3, and described by Schönau et al. [5].

Figure 3: Parent Project Structure implemented in the NFDI4Ing RDMO for collecting DMPs within SPP 2419 HyCAM

The coordination project serves as the primary parent project for the ten individual projects, each of which in turn acts as a parent for its respective subprojects represented by each project member. The multilevel structure provides benefits at different scales. At the program level, aggregated information supports the development of overarching guidelines for data handling, confidentiality, and collaboration agreements. At the researcher level, individual DMPs enable monitoring of implementation progress and facilitate targeted support. At the same time, researchers retain full autonomy to create and maintain their own DMPs within this coordinated framework. Through the RDMO parent-project function, project members can access DMPs within their projects, while the Coordination team maintains oversight across all ten projects. This centralized yet flexible approach strengthens transparency, fosters good RDM practices, and enhances collaboration across subprojects.

To ensure harmonized and compliant DMP preparation across the program, detailed guidance for using the NFDI4Ing RDMO platform has been developed and made accessible to all HyCAM members.

3. Software Code Management

The DFG Priority Program SPP 2419 *Hydrogen-based Fuel Combustion using Additive Manufacturing* (HyCAM) integrates combustion science and additive manufacturing within an interdisciplinary research framework. Its objective is to exploit the design flexibility of additive manufacturing to develop optimized, efficient, and safe hydrogen-based combustion systems. By fostering collaboration across chemistry, combustion, materials science, modeling, and advanced manufacturing, HyCAM generates heterogeneous research outputs, including experimental datasets, simulation results, numerical models, design tools, and data-processing pipelines.

In this context, software and source code represent core research artefacts rather than auxiliary tools. Simulation codes for reactive flows, data-processing scripts for advanced diagnostics, optimization routines for additively manufactured burner geometries, and multi-physics modeling workflows directly underpin scientific conclusions and engineering decisions.

To ensure transparency, traceability, and reproducibility across institutions and disciplines, it is recommended to manage all project-related software and text-based research artefacts in structured Git repositories. Git-based version control provides the technical and organizational framework required for compliant research data management. Beyond version tracking, Git repositories directly support the FAIR principles for research software:

- **Findability** is enhanced through structured repository organization, metadata, and persistent project documentation.
- **Accessibility** is ensured via controlled but standardized access mechanisms within institutional infrastructures.
- **Interoperability** is facilitated through documented dependencies, standardized file formats, and transparent configuration management.
- **Reusability** is enabled by versioned releases, clear licensing information, comprehensive documentation, and the possibility to reference specific commits in publications and datasets.

By systematically linking code versions to generated datasets and published results, Git-based management ensures full reproducibility of computational workflows and strengthens long-term knowledge transfer within HyCAM.

4. Research Data Storage and Documentation: Coscine as central data infrastructure

For the practical implementation of the data management strategy within SPP 2419 HyCAM Project, [Coscine](#) can serve as the central platform. It is the default platform for documenting, organizing, storing, and archiving scientific outputs generated within the program. These include peer-reviewed publications, curated validation datasets, experimental measurement data, simulation input files, simulation results, and related documentation.

Coscine provides a secure, institutionally hosted environment that enables structured data storage, controlled collaboration across project partners, and long-term preservation of research outputs for up to ten years after project completion. Individual **persistent identifiers (PIDs)** can be assigned to datasets, enabling controlled sharing with external collaborators and supporting traceability across projects. By design, Coscine supports the FAIR principles and offers the following key features:

- **Storage:** Access to institutional storage resources (depending on organizational and project affiliation).
- **Collaboration:** Controlled access for all authorized project members.
- **Metadata Management:** Structured and automatically linked metadata associated with each project and dataset.
- **Custom Metadata Profiles:** Project-specific metadata schemas adaptable to disciplinary requirements.
- **Long-term Archiving:** In-place archiving of project data for a minimum of ten years.

4.1 Coscine structure and role-based access control

Coscine employs a hierarchical, tree-like organizational model. Each structure consists of two types of nodes:

- **Project nodes**, which define and document the logical structure of the data;
- **Resource nodes**, which represent the storage layer and contain the actual uploaded data.

Resource nodes correspond to datasets and may contain complete folder structures. Project (and sub-project) nodes serve primarily organizational and documentation purposes. Different resource types are available to accommodate various data formats and storage backends, as specified in the Coscine

documentation. A list of all resource types available and their specification can be found on the corresponding help page of [Coscine](#).

Coscine implements role-based access control with three permission levels: **Owner**, **Member**, and **Guest**.

- **Owners** have full read/write access and can manage project settings and permissions.
- **Members** have read/write access and can create project and resource nodes.
- **Guests** have read-only access and may view or download data.

Access permissions are defined individually at the project-node level and are not automatically inherited from parent nodes. This ensures fine-grained control aligned with project-specific confidentiality and governance requirements. More details about the access permission can be found on the help page of [Coscine](#) regarding this aspect.

The hierarchical structure proposed for SPP 2419 HyCAM is illustrated in Figure 4. Analogous to the structure used in the NFDI4Ing RDMO, the baseline architecture consists of a central coordination node at the top level, with individual projects organized at the second hierarchical level.

Figure 4: Schematic of the proposed hierarchical structure implementation in Coscine for SPP 2419 HyCAM

The coordination project serves as the top-level parent node within the HyCAM Coscine structure and provides overarching visibility across all ten individual projects and their respective sub-projects. Each of the ten projects is, in turn, configured as a parent node for its associated sub-projects, ensuring a clear hierarchical organization. Within this framework, project coordinators assign researchers and principal investigators (PIs) to their respective project nodes with appropriate managerial permissions. This role-based allocation ensures clear responsibility, structured governance, and controlled access at each hierarchical level. At the second hierarchical level, all members assigned to the same project have visibility of the sub-projects created within that project once the corresponding parent node has been defined. This setup facilitates transparent internal data sharing while maintaining separation between distinct projects. The resulting structure represents a pragmatic and scalable solution for coordinated data collection, documentation, and collaboration within each HyCAM project. Each project member can then create their own sub-project node, in which they can upload different resources, following the procedure and guidelines prepared and provided by the coordination project.

4.2 Workflow in Coscine

Research data management (RDM) within Coscine typically follows the structured workflow outlined below:

1. Generation, structuring, and documentation of research data
2. Creation of an appropriate project node within the hierarchical structure
3. Application for and allocation of suitable storage resources
4. Creation of one or more resource nodes for data storage
5. Upload and metadata annotation of datasets
6. Archiving

The workflow begins prior to the actual use of Coscine, at the stage of data generation, where a consistent and meaningful data structure must be defined and appropriate documentation established. Data generation comprises both raw data, and processed data derived from these sources. A clear distinction between raw and processed data is strongly recommended to ensure traceability and reproducibility. Establishing a well-defined data structure at this early stage enhances data usability, facilitates metadata creation, and significantly simplifies the subsequent upload.

Once the data have been generated, structured, and properly documented, an appropriate project node must be created in Coscine, if not already existing. During the creation process, mandatory metadata fields must be completed to ensure consistent documentation and traceability. As access permissions are not automatically inherited from parent project nodes, user roles must be explicitly assigned at each level. Detailed instructions for user management and role assignment are available in the official [Coscine documentation](#).

Storage requirements can be reliably assessed once the data have been generated, structured, and documented. Based on these requirements, an appropriate resource type must be selected within Coscine, as different resource types correspond to different storage backends and technical configurations. Comprehensive descriptions of the available resource types, including a decision-support flowchart, are provided in the official Coscine documentation. For certain storage options, such as S3 resources or web storage exceeding 25 GB, a formal application process is required. The relevant application forms are accessible via the [Coscine help pages](#). Each HyCAM member may apply for storage resources up to 125 TB. Detailed guidance for creating resource nodes is available in the official [Coscine documentation](#). The essential steps include i) selecting the appropriate resource type; ii) choosing a suitable metadata (application) profile, and iii) completing the required resource metadata fields. The choice of resource type should be based on the intended storage backend and data characteristics, following the decision guidance provided in the [Coscine documentation](#).

A **metadata profile** defines the structured set of metadata fields used to describe a dataset. Metadata (i.e., structured information stored alongside the actual data) enhances findability, interpretability, and reproducibility. For this reason, the assignment of comprehensive metadata to all uploaded datasets is mandatory within HyCAM.

In Coscine, metadata profiles serve as discipline-adapted implementations of established metadata schemata. They define the fields available for describing files within a resource node and must be selected when the resource is created. As the metadata profile cannot be changed retroactively for existing files, careful selection at the time of configuration is essential. Metadata are a central element of FAIR-compliant research data management. They ensure:

- **Findability**, through structured and searchable descriptions;

- **Reproducibility**, by documenting context, parameters, and dependencies;
- **Reusability**, by providing sufficient methodological transparency.

Comprehensive information on the metadata (application) profiles available in Coscine can be found in the official [Coscine documentation](#). A brief overview of the most relevant profiles is provided below. Multiple metadata profiles are available within Coscine and are maintained via institutional GitLab repositories.

Base Metadata Profile

The *Base* metadata profile is derived from the DataCite Metadata Schema (Kernel 4.0), a widely adopted cross-disciplinary standard for describing research data. It includes three mandatory fields (Title, Creator, Creation Date) and two optional fields (Subject Area, Type).

The Base profile provides the minimum required metadata for potential DOI assignment and is recommended as a starting point for creating customized profiles. However, as it does not contain discipline-specific fields, its capacity to fully support detailed engineering documentation is limited.

EngMeta Metadata Profile

EngMeta is a metadata profile specifically designed for engineering research data. Developed within the DIPL-ING project, it enables structured documentation of:

- Recorded and controlled variables,
- System components and boundary conditions,
- Measurement and simulation parameters (e.g., temporal and spatial resolution),
- Software, instruments, computational environments, and
- The broader research process and actors involved.

EngMeta is particularly suited for large or technically complex datasets and is therefore recommended for most combustion and additive manufacturing research outputs within HyCAM.

Custom Metadata Profiles

If no existing metadata profile adequately reflects the specific requirements of a project, researchers may create a customized metadata profile using the [Coscine metadata profile generator](#). Custom profiles should remain aligned with FAIR principles and, where possible, build upon established standards to ensure interoperability and long-term usability.

At the end of the data lifecycle, datasets must be formally archived. Within Coscine, **archiving** is implemented by setting the corresponding resource to read-only status, thereby preventing further modification while preserving accessibility for authorized users. Archiving ensures long-term preservation of research data for a minimum of ten years, in accordance with institutional policies and principles of good scientific practice. Detailed guidance on the archiving procedure is available in the official [Coscine documentation](#).

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